

OneGeochemistry Interim Governance

OneGeochemistry is an international collaboration between multiple national and international organisations that support geochemistry capability and data production.

Mission statement: Advance geoscientific knowledge and discoveries by building and maintaining consensus-driven standards that make geochemistry research data globally findable and accessible, and truly interoperable and reusable to both humans and machines.

Vision: OneGeochemistry seeks to create a global geochemical data network that facilitates and promotes discovery of, and access to, geochemical data through coordination and collaboration among international geochemical data providers.

Based on the successful model of OneGeology, the OneGeochemistry initiative was first proposed at SciDataCon in 2019 in Beijing ([Lehnert et al. 2019](#)). Following that meeting, an informal network was formed by a group of dedicated geochemists around the globe, representing national and international geochemistry data infrastructures.

This informal group was awarded a European Commission grant under a larger initiative of the International Science Council's Committee on Data (CODATA). The applicants of the OneGeochemistry work package of the WorldFAIR project, each representing a geochemistry data infrastructure, have formed an interim Board of governance active **since the 20th of May 2022** (full member description in Table 1). A chair will be selected from within this group and rotated through the board members on a bimonthly basis. Should any board member step down while this interim governance is in place, they are to be replaced with a new representative of the respective data infrastructure. Since December 2022, the OneGeochemistry initiative is acting as the OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group for a period of two years. This Working Group will be utilised to recruit a representative membership base to the initiative that will then be able to vote on a long-term governance structure for OneGeochemistry. ***This interim board will be in place until such a governance structure has been established.***

Kind regards,

Kerstin Lehnert, Marthe Klöcking, Kirsten Elger, Lesley Wyborn, Dominik Hezel,
Lucia Profeta, Angus Nixon

Table 1: Members of the interim board for OneGeochemistry and the projects or activities they represent.

Name of Board Member	Name of Project or Activity	Short description
Kerstin Lehnert	Astromat (2018-2028)	Kerstin is director of the Astromaterials Data System (https://www.astromat.org), a US-based, NASA-funded data facility since 2019 that provides data services for astromaterials sample data.
Marthe Klöcking	DIGIS (2021-2024)	Marthe is coordinator of the 'Digital Geochemical Data Infrastructure (DIGIS) for GEOROC 2.0' (http://digis.geo.uni-goettingen.de), a project funded by the DFG (German Research Foundation) to align the GEOROC database with FAIR principles. GEOROC (https://georoc.eu) has been compiling global geochemical data since 1999 and collaborates closely with EarthChem. GEOROC data is also available via the EarthChem Portal.
Kirsten Elger	GFZ Data Services; EPOS Multi-scale laboratories (2016-2030)	Kirsten is repository manager of GFZ Data Services (https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/), the domain repository for geosciences data hosted at GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences and partner repository of the EPOS Multi-scale laboratories (https://epos-msl.uu.nl/). The EPOS Thematic Core Service Multi-scale Laboratories is a community of European Solid Earth sciences laboratories including high-temperature and -pressure experimental facilities, electron microscopy, micro-beam analysis, analogue tectonic and geodynamic modelling, paleomagnetism, and analytical laboratories (https://epos-msl.uu.nl/ ; https://www.epos-eu.org/). Kirsten is also a member of the Specialised Information Service Geosciences (https://www.fidgeo.de/en/), a participant of the National Research Data Infrastructure for the Earth Sciences (NFDI4Earth) in Germany (https://www.nfdi4earth.de).
Lesley Wyborn	AuScope Virtual Research Environments (2018-2025)	Lesley is a participant in the Australian AuScope Virtual Research Environments (AVRE) Program, which is a rich ecosystem of FAIR data and tools that are contributed by a diverse range of Australian research and government organisations. AVRE aims to enable interoperability across multiple disciplines including geochemistry, geophysics, geospatial and

		environmental sciences. Lesley is a participant in many international arenas such as RDA, COPDESS, CODATA, AGU, EGU and ESIP (https://www.auscope.org.au/avre ; https://earthsciences.anu.edu.au/)
Dominik Hezel	NFDI4Earth (2021-2026)	Dominik leads the group for Data Science at Institute for Geosciences (IfG) at the Goethe University Frankfurt and is the Co-Spokesperson for the Commons Measure within the National Research Data Infrastructure for the Earth Sciences (NFDI4Earth) in Germany (https://www.nfdi4earth.de). His research area is Cosmochemistry and Meteoritics. He is also the lab-manager of the EPMA/SEM/ μ .XRF laboratories at the IfG.
Lucia Profeta	EarthChem (2006-2027)	Lucy is product manager of EarthChem (https://www.earthchem.org), a US-based, NSF funded data facility that has worked over the past 15 years with a federation of geochemical databases including PetDB, GEOROC, NAVDAT, USGS, and the Japanese DARWIN database to provide central access to geochemical data via the EarthChem Portal. EarthChem led the Editors Roundtable and COPDESS to build consensus around best practices for geochemical data and developed the EarthChemXML as a schema for data exchange.
Angus Nixon	AuScope Geochemistry Network (2019-2025)	Angus is the inorganic geochemistry model leader and project leader in Australian geological survey vocabulary standardisation for the AuScope Geochemistry Network (AGN), established in 2019. The AGN is an Australian consortium of Earth Science institutes cooperating to develop national geochemistry research infrastructure, and an Australian network of geochemical laboratories that contribute data to AusGeochem, a FAIR data platform enabling researchers to solve the national challenges of today and tomorrow. (https://www.auscope.org.au/agn , https://www.auscope.org.au/ausgeochem)

References:

Lehnert, K.A, Wyborn, L., Bennett, V.C., Hezel, D., McInnes, B.I.A, Plank, T., Rubin, K., 2019. OneGeochemistry: Towards an Interoperable Global Network of FAIR Geochemical Data. SciDataCon 2019, https://conference.codata.org/CODATA_2019/sessions/88/paper/536/ Accessed 25 April 2022.